

Escrow as a Mechanism for Securing the Performance of Obligations

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Abstract

In the contemporary economic environment—characterized by volatility, the proliferation of remote contractual relations, and an escalation of risks related to non-performance of obligations—the issue of ensuring the secure and reliable execution of contractual terms has become increasingly prominent. Within this framework, the escrow institution has garnered growing attention as a legal mechanism that provides a safeguard for the interests of both contracting parties.

Escrow serves to mitigate risks associated with the unilateral breach of obligations by involving a neutral third-party agent to hold funds, documents, or other assets in trust. These assets are then disbursed to the designated beneficiary only upon the fulfillment of specified contractual conditions. This mechanism is widely regarded as an effective instrument in transactions involving significant financial or property interests, particularly in domains such as real estate, corporate law, international trade, information technology, and venture capital.

Keywords

Escrow, contract, obligation, performance, civil law, settlements, liability.

The study of the genesis of the escrow agreement directs researchers to recognize this legal construct as originating from the Anglo-Saxon legal system. The concept of escrow, or conditional deposit, was first implemented in the United States during the 1930s, amidst the Great Depression, when the practice of conditional deposits began to develop in the mortgage sector. In 1934, the U.S. Congress enacted the National Housing Act, which led to the establishment of the Federal Housing Administration and the Federal Housing Insurance Corporation. These institutions functioned as guarantors of loan obligations before banks. During this period, the concept of escrow emerged as a legal relationship involving the creditor, the debtor, and a third party, with the third party assuming the responsibility of ensuring the fulfillment of the obligation.

The legal dictionary defines the term "escrow" (Eng. escrow) in Anglo-American law as the act of depositing a sum of money in the name of a second party for the benefit of a third party, with the condition that it will only be released upon the fulfillment of the agreed-upon terms[1]. The content of this arrangement typically involves the conclusion of

contracts with the involvement of a third party—the escrow agent—who, through their actions, ensures the proper performance of the contract by the parties. This type of contract embodies a system of norms aimed at reducing the legal and economic risks that arise in the exercise of the parties' subjective civil rights.

In the United States, the active development of the escrow institution occurred as a result of the widespread use of the mortgage institution, which led to the necessity of creating a mechanism to protect the participants of such contracts through legislative action. To this day, escrow practices continue in the U.S., where an escrow account is separately opened from the mortgage (loan) account, into which, typically, payments for property taxes and insurance premiums are deposited in accordance with special conditions. The role of the escrow agent is to monitor that these funds are used solely for their intended purposes. In many cases, opening an escrow account when formalizing a mortgage is mandatory, as it guarantees to the creditor that the mortgagor will not fail to pay property taxes[2].

In foreign practice, escrow accounts are actively used in the formation of real estate contracts, securities contracts, and agreements related to valuable movable property and mortgage loans. For instance, in Germany, this type of account is widely used in the conclusion of mortgage-backed loan agreements. After receiving a mortgage loan, the borrower deposits a certain sum of money into the escrow account. These funds are then used by the bank that provided the mortgage loan to cover the principal amount and interest on the loan[3].

Swiss civil law defines an escrow agreement as follows: in accordance with this agreement, one party (the escrow agent) undertakes the obligation to receive certain property from the second party (the depositor), that is, the person bound by the primary obligation, to hold it in safekeeping, and to transfer it to a third party (the beneficiary) upon the fulfillment of the agreed conditions or the performance of the actions specified in the primary obligation. Furthermore, the depositor and the beneficiary are obliged to pay the agreed-upon compensation to the escrow agent under the terms of the contract[4].

The terms "escrow," "escrow account," and "escrow agent" are closely related. The key element in ensuring the escrow mechanism is the "person" acting as the escrow agent. This is an independent third party that offers its services to the parties and implements the mechanism of securing the transaction through escrow. The concept of involving a third party is not new; however, in this case, the third party not only acts in the interest of the creditor but also serves as a neutral party in the contract, representing the interests of both sides. This approach enhances the level of protection for the parties' interests[5].

In the United Arab Emirates, escrow agent services are mandatory for all real estate contracts. According to the laws of the Emirate of Dubai, agents must be banks or financial institutions licensed by the Central Bank of the UAE to accept deposits, and they must also obtain additional accreditation and permission from the Dubai Land Department. Thus, UAE legislation provides for a restricted list of escrow agents, ensuring protection

against improper execution of contractual obligations by the parties involved. This, in turn, guarantees the proper functioning of civil and commercial transactions within the country.

In the United Kingdom, the obligations of escrow agents are thoroughly regulated, with these agents often being lawyers. For example, if an escrow agent fails to properly fulfill their obligations under an escrow agreement, they may be held liable for penalties, compensation for any damage caused to both parties, and exclusion from any legal practice. As a result, no lawyer would risk legal violations, as doing so could lead to the loss of client trust and significant financial costs[6].

Considering the development of these relations, escrow practices abroad are regulated by various legal norms; however, the essence of the agreement remains unchanged: the party to the contract who is required to make payment will, under certain conditions, receive the payment not from the second party to the contract, but from a third party.

Based on the aforementioned, in the case of an escrow account, the escrow agent is a bank, not another person (such as a lawyer, notary, etc.). The bank, as a highly trusted entity, opens a special escrow account, where it holds and blocks the funds received from the depositor (account holder), and these funds are transferred to the beneficiary once the conditions specified in the contract are met.

The national legislation only introduced one type of escrow—escrow accounts—so only banks can act as escrow agents, and the method of securing the obligation can only involve non-cash monetary funds.

According to P. Oleynik, in the future, the escrow algorithm in Ukraine should look as follows:

The parties to the primary obligation will enter into an escrow agreement with the escrow agent (essentially acting as an intermediary between the seller and the buyer). This will typically be a tripartite agreement concluded simultaneously with the primary obligation;

The buyer transfers the contract amount to the escrow agent's (escrow account) at the bank. Typically, the escrow account is a special bank account opened in the name of the escrow agent, who will hold the funds transferred by the buyer (depositor) and later transfer them to the seller (beneficiary). The escrow agent can only use the funds in this account to transfer them to the seller or return them to the buyer. Sometimes, the parties require periodic reporting from the escrow agent on the status of this account;

The seller provides the escrow agent with the documents that must be transferred under the primary obligation (such as the transfer of shares, company founding documents, property ownership confirmation documents, etc.), as the transfer of these documents is a key condition for fulfilling the obligation;

The escrow agent checks whether the form and content of the documents provided align with the terms of the primary obligation. If the documents meet these requirements, the escrow agent transfers them to the buyer and releases the contract sum to the seller. If

the documents do not meet the required conditions, the escrow agent returns them to the seller and reimburses the buyer for the contract sum. In this case, the transaction is considered terminated. If this does not contradict the escrow and primary obligation terms, the escrow agent may give the seller additional time to adjust the documents to meet the primary obligation requirements, after which everything will proceed according to the above scheme[7].

In light of the practices established in banks regarding escrow, the subject of the escrow agreement involves the actions of the depositor, who entrusts funds to the escrow agent for safekeeping, and the obligations of the escrow agent to ensure the safekeeping of the funds and transfer them to the beneficiary when the conditions outlined in the agreement are met. The object of the escrow agreement is non-cash funds, as all banking services are related to operations involving these funds.

Reforming the civil legislation in Uzbekistan concerning the regulation of bank accounts is undoubtedly a positive and long-awaited development. An analysis of the traditional methods of applying escrow agreements in foreign countries and changes in local civil legislation shows that the domestic legislator has introduced only one form of escrow—namely, the escrow account—where the bank acts as the escrow agent, and non-cash funds are used exclusively as the means of securing obligations. This confirms that the legal application of the escrow institution in Uzbekistan is much narrower compared to the legislation of foreign countries.

Despite some inconsistencies and criticisms of the civil legislation, it can be confidently stated that certain aspects of aligning the local business environment with international standards are moving forward. For example, the escrow account agreement is a universal and adaptable legal structure aimed at securing the primary obligations arising from a civil legal contract. If the escrow account agreement is concluded between a bank and a depositor, it is a public, consensual, bilateral (synallagmatic), payable, term-based, and fiduciary agreement. Furthermore, it should be emphasized that the escrow account agreement is prospective and likely to find its place in the local legal system in the near future.

It should be noted that during a video conference on September 23, 2024, chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, discussing measures for the development of the construction industry and construction materials, the introduction of a guaranteed "escrow" system for the purchase of housing to prevent fraud and misunderstandings in housing construction was mentioned[8].

At the same time, the draft of the new edition of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan also includes provisions related to escrow contracts. This indicates that actions have begun in Uzbekistan to actively incorporate escrow into banking practices and develop effective mechanisms for its use. Therefore, explaining the essence of escrow as a method of ensuring the fulfillment of obligations and determining its place within the system of civil-law contracts is of significant importance.

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